

THE MEANING OF GREEK-LATIN PREFIXES IN MEDICAL TERMINOLOGY

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Abstract: The thesis offers an overview of the status quo of medical terminology. It is obvious that a basic understanding of Greek-Latin prefixes increases the productivity of learning and comfort while using medical terminology. A knowledge of the meaning of prefixes enables the students to thoroughly analyse a given medical term in terms of its component parts. The main part of this thesis consists of examples containing the most common prefixes.

Key words: Latin, Greek, language of medicine, medical terminology.

Over the centuries, the development of medical terminology has been based on the process of creating parallel national and international terms, known all over the world and well-defined. In the field of medical, biological and pharmaceutical sciences, such a reliable tool of communication was Latin and Greek.

Medical Latin enables the use of multilingual specialist literature. It is indispensable in communication with scientists from other countries. It enables us to precisely define and differentiate between colleagues. The benefits flowing from knowledge of Latin are so significant that it seems impossible to imagine a physician, pharmacist or physiotherapist without even elementary knowledge of this language. Nonetheless, fluent command of the vocabulary requires a lot of effort. Learning numerous names and terms without philological preparation is time-consuming; moreover, it usually leads to establishing a mechanical bond between specific terms and a set of letters or syllables. This method of acquiring language competence is not sufficient or satisfactory, because vocabulary acquired in such a way is easily forgotten. It is even easier to twist the terms.

The aim of the present thesis is to offer a remedy for the difficulties mentioned before, or at least, to familiarise the reader with medical vocabulary. Understanding of the etymological and morphological mechanisms is a simple way to acquire and remember the most curious phrases.

Today, the dominant language of science is English. All the most influential medical journals are written in English, and English has become the language of

international conferences. We have entered the era of medical English, which resembles the era of medical Latin in that, once again, physicians have chosen a single language for international communication. Note, however, that English is rooted in the classical languages. It is estimated that about 90% of the medical vocabulary in English is of Greek or Latin origin. One cannot deny the huge impact of ancient Greek on medical terminology.

This review may be helpful in this respect and it might form the basis for learning medical terminology in other languages, especially in English.

a- *atonia* - the absence of tone; *apnoe* - the absence of breath; *aplasia* - an organ, tissue or body part didn't develop normally.

dys- *dyspepsia* - disorder of digestion; *dyspnoe* - difficult respiration; *dystrophia* - faulty or inadequate nutrition or development.

hyper- *hyperaemia* - excess of blood in a body part; *hypertonia* - increased rigidity, tension, and spasticity of the muscles; *hyperthermia* - an abnormally high body temperature

hypo- *hypochondriasis* - an abnormally heightened and unreasonable fear of disease; *hypodermis* - a layer of cells beneath the epidermis in some plants; *hypothermia* - abnormally low body temperature.

peri- *pericardium* - serous membrane surrounding the heart; *periosteum* - membrane surrounding a bone; *peristalsis* - rhythmic contraction of the digestive tract.

intra- *intracellular* - within the cell; *intrarectal* - within the rectum; *intrauterine* - within the uterus; *intravenous*- in, into, within a vein.

Conclusion. The consistency and perfection of Latin and Greek languages allows to express in one word the concept given in several words in Uzbek language. For example: *dysentery* – bad intestine or *symbiosis* – living together of two or more organisms. Greek-Latin prefixes play an important role in word formation. Knowing the means and methods of word formation is of great importance in learning medical terms.

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